

Child-Robot Conversation in the Wild Wild Home: A Language Processing User Study

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Abstract—Child-robot interaction (CRI) has been mostly studied in labs and classroom settings. In this work, we share a CRI language processing study carried out in children’s homes. Any automated system deployed “in-the-wild” faces practical problems, but when the target users are children, these problems get even more sensitive and challenging. In this work we analyse how each language processing layer performs with children at home with no researcher present. We carried out an experiment with 7 families [N=14 children, 6-13 years old] cohabiting with a simulated robot for 2 weeks in their own homes. Our goal in this study is to evaluate the performance of voice recognition, language understanding and dialogue management when children interact with a robot at home. Our results indicate that dialogue management capabilities are becoming the key element in the language processing pipeline; they also denote that the dialogue engine should include mixed-initiative capabilities and show the relative usage of different common built-in intents.

I. INTRODUCTION

The field of natural language processing has made tremendous progress in areas spanning from speech recognition and language understanding to dialogue management. However, there are some barriers that make these tasks particularly challenging within a children’s context. In speech recognition, multiple factors make children’s voice inherently difficult to process, from the physical features derived from their smaller vocal tracts to their variable usage of language as they grow up and learn, as described by Potaminos, Narayanan and Lee [1], and Russell and D’Arcy [2]. Besides these unavoidable limiting factors, the scarcity of public children-specific large datasets make the development of speech recognition solutions even more challenging and usually tackled only by large corporations, as in Liao *et al.*’s work [3]. Language understanding for children’s intents is also more challenging than doing so with adults. As pointed out by Gray *et al.* [4], “*Children are also more likely to use imaginative words, ungrammatical phrases, incorrect pronunciations, and be interested in different genres than adults, presenting challenges for language modeling*”.

We bring this unique issue to the forefront in an even more unpredictable and under-studied user setting: children’s

homes. In van Straten, Peter and Kühne’s [5] review of papers published between 2000 and 2017, the authors could only find one study taking place in children’s homes. Additionally, only more recently have researchers focused on this venue for longer periods of time. Zhao and McEwen [6] and Michaelis and Mutlu [7] described experiments that investigated the usage of robots as reading companions. In the first experiment, the kids used commercial robots at home for 180 days, whereas the second experiment lasted two weeks.

Notice that the limited number of CRI studies carried out at children’s homes contrasts with the ample set of works found for non-embodied (i.e., non robots) conversational agents (CAs). Garg *et al.*’s [8] survey of CAs papers reported up to 13 works whose focus were precisely the home and family context. While most of those works focus on design and usability, some of them analyse different aspects of the language processing pipeline. Beneteau *et al.* [9], studied communication breakdowns with an Alexa device and described several repair strategies used by children and families. Xu and Warschauer [10] provided a detailed performance analysis of the language processing pipeline for a joint reading scenario. The same authors shared in [11] an experiment where they explored children responses to open-ended questions and suggested to assign multiple intents to the possible responses to maximize the specificity of the system’s feedback. In Monarca *et al.* [12], researchers demonstrated that the communication design in terms of response time thresholds should be adapted to the children’s language abilities.

Our work builds on top of these previous studies, analysing the language processing performance when children interact with a robot in children’s homes. We carried out a two-week experiment with 7 families and 14 children, as detailed in section III. In order to do that, we made use of Haru4Kids (H4K), an app-based robot presented in section II-A, whose language processing module is detailed in section II-B. We included a set of activities with different degrees of interactivity, whose description can be found in III-C. Two surveys were conducted with parents and kids, one before and another one after the experiment. The insights derived from these surveys were published in [13].

In this work we analyse the relative performance of each layer on the language processing pipeline, trying to influence future research directions. As part of this analysis, we

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Fig. 1: *Haru4Kids*: (a) iPad supported by rotating-tabletop stand, and (b) high-level technical description of the system.

investigate what type of dialogue strategy is more appreciated by the user (user-driven vs system-driven vs mixed-initiative) and we evaluate the usage of different common built-in intents. The results of the study are detailed in section IV, and the contributions derived from those results are summarized in section VI.

II. HARU4KIDS

A. Platform and Software Architecture

The H4K platform simulates Haru robot [14] capabilities on a tablet PC. The main motivation to create this platform was to minimize the risks inherent to hardware deployment at children’s homes, as explained in section III-D.

H4K consists of a Haru avatar displayed on an iPad supported by a rotating stand (Fig.1a). This rotating stand is connected to the app’s computer vision component, following the children as they move with two degrees of freedom: roll and yaw angles.

The app is designed to work on the iPad and uses several *Apple*-specific libraries. At the highest level of abstraction, the application is divided into seven main modules: User Interface, Conversation Manager, Vision Manager, Central Controller, Settings Manager, Logging, and Stand Manager (Fig.1b). The Central Controller acts as the coordinator of the app’s behavior, interacting with other modules and accessing the *cloud* as needed.

B. Conversation Manager

The Conversation Manager handles the components needed for voice-based interactions. For speech recognition and synthesis, the Conversation Manager makes use of *Apple*’s built-in libraries and its default configuration and models for Spanish: no domain-specific fine-tuning was done. On the other hand, dialogue management did require a custom development. Currently there is no suitable commercial solution that provides the capabilities required for the kind of interactions offered by the physical Haru prototype [15]. Specifically, in commercial applications, system-initiated subdialogues are usually not available or limited to simple question-response short interactions typical of chatbot applications.

H4K’s Conversation Manager makes use of DialogFlow’s [16] intent identification and entity extraction module (*i.e.*, as

the Natural Language Understanding -NLU- layer). However, in order to allow for full-fledged mixed-initiative conversations, dialogue management is performed by a custom-developed dialogue container hosted in Amazon Web Services (AWS) that substitutes and expands the dialogue capabilities provided by Dialogflow.

Besides providing mixed-initiative capabilities, H4K’s Dialogue Container brings other advantages. First, it includes a clear separation between back-end logic and dialogue configuration. Second, in this module we added some domain-independent dialogue capabilities that are particularly useful for error-prone scenarios like ours in the wild. Specifically:

- **Repeat**: Users could ask H4K at anytime to repeat its last utterance.
- **Help**: Users could ask for help and content creators could define context-sensitive help responses.
- **Background**: This mechanism gets triggered in mixed-initiative dialogues when there is neither a system-driven proactive utterance nor a user-driven request. Typically, it would trigger a prompt like “*Is there anything else I can do for you?*”.
- **Sleep**: This built-in intent allows the user to pause the app at anytime, sending the robot to sleep. This intent would be triggered by user inputs like “*Go to sleep*” or “*Pause*”.

III. EXPERIMENTS

A. Participants and setup

A total of 7 families from Spain participated in the study. We used convenience recruitment, making use of researchers’ contacts and word of mouth. All participants were native Spanish speakers and the app was fully developed and configured to work in Spanish.

In total, H4K engaged with 14 children ($n_{male} = 9$) between the ages of 6 and 13 ($\mu_{age} = 9.6$). Besides one family with an only child, the other six families had at least two children. Taking into account periods of time when the children were not at home (vacations or living in multiple households), the robot cohabited with each family for an average of 20 days ($\sigma = 5.9$, $\max = 27$), yielding a net period of two weeks.

The decision for the specific sample size is supported by the fact that this kind of exploratory study is typically performed with smaller sample sizes than the ones in experimental research, as pointed out by [17]. This choice is similar to previous long-term CRI studies *e.g.*, $N = 19$ children [18] and $N = 14$ children [19].

Researchers went to each family’s home, and after informing them in detail about the experiment, gathered their participation agreement forms, set-up the system, and explained to the parents how to configure the level of information sharing. Then, the researchers gave a brief introduction on how to use the platform to all family members, however left children to explore H4K’s characteristics and features on their own. In particular, no details were given in terms of dialogue capabilities: no reference to mixed-initiative support and no

explanation about the *Repeat* or *Help* intents described in section II-A.

Participants interacted with the system through the tablet’s microphone and speakers. That is, no external headset or earphone was used to improve the interaction.

B. Data collection

All the events occurring during the execution of the application were logged in real-time, both locally in the tablet and on the cloud (by *Cloudwatch* –CW, from *AWS Cloud* [20]). These logs gathered all relevant information for our CRI study, including the speech recognition outcomes, the intents recognized by the NLU component, the ongoing activity, and the initiator of subdialogue (user-driven vs system-driven).

C. H4K activities

By default, H4K was in sleeping mode. Children could wake it up by clicking on a “wake up” button, as shown in figure 2.

Fig. 2: Child waking up H4K

Once waken up, H4K would initiate a short small-talk conversation after which it would proactively suggest one of the pre-configured entertainment-educative activities which are described in the following list:

- **Storytelling:** H4K tells a story while displaying specific illustrations on the screen.
- **Gusano Loco (“Crazy Worm”):** H4K tells the user to suggest words within different categories and after compiling a list of words, fits it in an incomplete story and tells the -usually humorous- resulting story.
- **Detective:** A list of words is given, and children need to identify the one word that does not match; for example: “apple, chair, banana, peach”.
- **Would you rather ...?:** H4K presents two silly options from which the user has to choose one; e.g., “Would you rather have three eyes or two noses?”.
- **Jokes:** H4K tells three child-friendly jokes in a row.

This selection of activities was diverse in terms of interactivity, with *Jokes* and *Storytelling* being mostly passive whereas the other required active participation from the users. The activities were also variable in terms of duration, from the short *Would you rather?* and *Jokes* to the longer *Storytelling*.

In our experiment we sought to evaluate how speech recognition accuracy may change depending on the type of question and activity. With that goal in mind we configured in H4K’s small-talk section a set of different system-driven questions classified depending on the expected answer: yes/no, multiple choice, and open/ended questions. Multiple choice questions were of the kind “do you prefer going to the beach or to the mountain?”, with only 2 choices available. While in small-talk mode, H4K would randomly select a question among these 3 types.

Besides the small-talk section, other activities also included some degree of interaction. *Would-you-rather* included multiple-choice questions with two alternatives per instance. The *detective*’s game also provided a set of alternatives for the child to choose (usually 4 or 5). Finally, *crazy-worms* interactions could also be considered multiple-choice questions, but in this case the range of possible answers could be much bigger, with questions from “tell me a day of the week” (7 alternatives) to “choose a number from 1 to 100” (100 alternatives) or even “choose a color” (theoretically unlimited but in practice allowing only some 20 variants).

D. Ethical Aspects

An Institutional Review Board (IRB) approval was obtained prior to the starting of the experiments. Caregivers provided consent and children ages 7 or older provided written assent.

To minimize the physical risks, all hardware deployed (both tablets and stands) were commercial solutions easily found in the market and largely used for other purposes.

Families were informed that they could opt-in for image and audio recording during their usage of H4K, but by default both image and audio options were deactivated. They were also informed that, even if they opted-in, no image or audio would ever be uploaded to the cloud and all media would be saved locally on the device. Only researchers included in the IRB clearance were allowed afterwards to access those images and audios for research purposes.

To avoid excessive usage, parents could configure H4K settings adapting the allowed usage time. By default, the system had no restriction, but parents were instructed how to modify that option if they wanted to.

H4K settings include a field that let families configure the age of the youngest kid at home. The activities were classified with the minimum appropriate age, so no content designed for older children was provided to younger ones.

As a compensation for their time, parents were given a gift-card for a popular online store and children were given some stickers.

The activities were designed under the supervision of a neuropsychologist with the main objective to stimulate children’s brains. The typology of activities is varied, in order to work different cognitive functions and capabilities, such as attention, memory, language, reasoning, comprehension, perception and processing speed.

IV. RESULTS

H4K was used a grand total of 18 hours and 22 minutes, with a family minimum of 53 minutes and a maximum of 4 hours and 55 minutes. There were a total of 519 sessions among all families. Only one family limited the usage time to afternoon-only, the rest of parents made H4K available 24/7. Four families opted-in for audio recording, so we collected 1209 recorded prompts from a total of 1981 prompts registered throughout the experiment.

The following sections describe the results obtained at different levels: speech recognition, language understanding, and dialogue management.

A. Children’s speech recognition in the wild

All recorded prompts were transcribed by native Spanish speakers, and then the Word Error Rate (WER) was calculated. The global WER was of 0.077. The detailed results classified by activity and type of question is depicted in Table I. The passive activities (*i.e.*, jokes and story telling, with hardly no children input) are not included in that table.

TABLE I: WER per type of question

	yes/no	multiple choice	open ended
Detectives	N/A	0.079	N/A
Crazy Worms	N/A	0.042	N/A
Would you rather	N/A	0.083	N/A
Smalltalk	0.065	0.043	0.114
TOTAL	0.065	0.054	0.114

As expected, WER is worse for open-ended questions. However, there is no significant difference between yes/no and multiple choice questions. An individual analysis of the errors pointed out that the robot name (“Haru”) appeared in 115 user inputs, and was misrecognized 40 times.

B. Children’s language understanding in the wild

Table II shows the intent recognition performance for the main intents of the application, grouped by “intent-type” and applying the usual metrics: precision, recall and F1-score. We also included $F(\beta = 0.5)$ since false positives are usually more harmful than false negatives in this context. For computing the different metrics while grouping categories, we used micro-average in order to smooth the impact of underrepresented classes (like the intent *Repeat*) on the total figures. In the table, column “multiple” groups together all possible answers to all multiple choice questions; “activity” refers to all user-driven inputs requesting to start a particular activity. In this table, *Help* is not included because that intent was triggered very few times and only by families that didn’t opt-in for audio recording.

The results shown in Table II describe a very robust NLU layer, with all intent types with $F(\beta = 0.5)$ above 0.97. This general conclusion, however, has to be contextualized by two factors: (1) in some cases the number of intent occurrences was too low, in particular *Repeat*. Table III shows the total count of intents as recognized by the NLU layer (True Positives -TP- and False Positives -FP-) and as

TABLE II: Intent Recognition Performance

	yes/no	multiple	sleep	repeat	activity
Precision	0.992	0.985	1.000	1.000	0.993
Recall	0.985	0.958	0.886	1.000	0.987
$F(\beta = 1)$	0.989	0.971	0.939	1.000	0.990
$F(\beta = 0.5)$	0.991	0.980	0.975	1.000	0.992

actually intended by the user (True Positives -TP- and False Negatives -FN-).

TABLE III: Intent Count

	yes/no	multiple	sleep	repeat	activity
NLU (TP+FP)	260	466	31	4	150
Users (TP+FN)	262	479	35	4	151

And (2), the intent recognition analysis above does not account for special situations unrelated to predefined intents. Specifically, it does not consider:

- **Recognition Errors:** Inputs where the automatic speech recognition (ASR) engine was not able to provide any transcription above its internal confidence threshold.
- **Silences:** Situations in which the ASR did not capture anything within the predefined time-frame (3.5 seconds), or when the user did not say anything (which is not an ASR error).
- **Out Of Scope (OOS):** The input could not be matched to any of the predefined intents. In some cases this was the expected behaviour: the open-ended questions were put in place to check the ASR performance, with no intention to process the input.

These three cases happened very often. Figure 3 shows the distribution of these situations depending on the question type. In the diagram, “expected” applies to responses that matched the question type (*e.g.*, “yes” or “no” for a yes/no question) and “other” refers to a valid in-domain intent other than the expected response (*e.g.*, the user asking for help, or requesting to launch another activity).

Figures 3(a) and 3(b) show that the expected inputs plus the in-scope “other” intents sum up to 76% of all the user responses both for yes/no and for multiple-choice questions. As mentioned above, notice that for open-ended questions, OOS was actually the expected kind of response.

Accurately identifying and handling OOS inputs is critical for the user experience [21]. Some commercial NLU systems, including Dialogflow’s, come with a “fallback” built-in intent that captures this kind of inputs. The performance analysis of this intent showed worse results compared to the other regular intents, but still above 0.9: Precision=0.902 (count of TP+FP=102) and Recall=0.979 (count of TP+FN=94) yielding F-scores of $F(\beta = 1)=0.939$ and $F(\beta = 0.5)=0.916$.

As part of the performance analysis, we also checked whether the number of errors were increasing or decreasing as the experiment went on. Figure 4 shows the percentage of recognition errors plus unexpected OOS inputs (*i.e.*, not as valid responses to open-ended questions) over the total

Fig. 3: *Response distribution*: (a) yes/no questions, (b) multiple-choice questions and (c) open-ended questions.

number of inputs. As depicted in the graph, there is a slight decreasing slope, but the percentage remains approximately constant at around 10%.

Fig. 4: Error percentage per day

The situation is, however, different when we focus on silence. Figure 5 shows the percentage of inputs “silence” out of the total number of inputs, with a moving average of 3 days to smooth the different usage in different days. This graph indicates that the silent inputs in the last days were much lower than in the first days.

C. Children-robot dialogue management in the wild

Typical dialogue evaluation frameworks like PARADISE [22], include objective usage metrics such as number of turns and dialogue duration. In this experiment, the average number of user turns per session was 5.250 ($\sigma = 8.39$), with a total of 78 sessions where children did not interact at all with the system (15% of the sessions). Figure 6 details the number of sessions grouped by number of user turns, showing 210 sessions (41% of the sessions) where children interacted precisely 3 times before finishing the session and 136 (26,20% of the sessions) with 4 or more user turns.

Regarding the duration of the sessions, the average time was 1 minute 55 seconds ($\sigma = 3$ minutes 31 seconds) with

Fig. 5: Silence inputs percentage per day

Fig. 6: Sessions per number of user turns

a maximum of 24 minutes and 55 seconds in one of the sessions. The average usage of the system was quite different between the families. As depicted in Table IV, one family used H4K on average around 47 seconds and 2.9 turns while another one had an average duration of almost 5 minutes and 11 turns per session.

TABLE IV: Time (in minutes) and number of turns per family and session

	F01	F02	F03	F04	F05	F06	F07
Time	3:06	2:38	1:24	1:32	3:39	4:58	0:47
Turns	9.60	4.85	4.28	4.28	10.59	11	2.95

Besides these standard metrics, we explored the usage of system-driven vs user-driven interactions and the domain-independent dialogue intents that were included in H4K.

As explained previously, H4K’s dialogue management provides mixed-initiative capabilities. Interactions always started in system-driven mode: H4K would initiate a short small-talk interaction after which it would suggest one of the activities at random. At any time, users could take control and proactively request one particular activity.

Figure 7 shows the evolution of the ratio “user requested” vs all activities (“system initiated” plus “user requested”). To smooth the impact of days with very little usage, the chart shows the ratio as a moving average with a window of 3

days. This graph indicates that children learned quickly how to take control and request what they wanted, so they used it more frequently as the experiment went on.

Fig. 7: User-initiated activities percentage over time

The usage of the domain-independent capabilities described in section II-A was irregular. The intents *Repeat* and *Help* were used very few times: *Repeat* was triggered 5 times in total, 3 of them by 1 family and the other 2 by 2 different families. *Help* was only triggered 3 times, 2 of them by the same family. The *Background* mechanism, however, was triggered very frequently: an accumulated total of 679 times, resulting in an average of 1.31 times per session ($\sigma = 1.98$).

Finally, regarding dialogue closure, users had 3 ways to stop the conversation: by using the built-in *Sleep* intent, by clicking on a “Go to sleep” button in the screen, or just by remaining silent for a prolonged period of time. Most of the times users just left H4K and let it stop by itself (337 times) whereas the usage of touch screen and voice was very similar (86 voice, 96 touch screen).

V. DISCUSSION

This work aimed at providing insights on child-robot interaction happening in the child’s home, specifically on the area of language processing. We explored the limitations of current solutions at voice recognition, language understanding, and dialogue management levels and tried to identify the best strategies to optimize the interaction.

A. Speech recognition

Voice recognition showed good results despite the very challenging conditions: children as users, recognition in the wild with frequent background noise, distant microphones, and non-English language. WER was below 0.07 for both yes/no and multiple choice questions, increasing to 0.11 for open-ended questions. These WER figures could probably be further improved by changing the avatar name “Haru” to a more frequent Spanish name, or by fine tuning the speech recognition models with this name.

In [23], the authors stated that “Typically, the most error-prone component of a spoken dialogue system is speech recognition” and designed their experiments so as to overcome this limitation and work only with perfect input recognition. Our results indicate that this statement might not be accurate anymore, at least for a setup and context like the one

described in our experiments. In fact, our results are aligned with the improvements reported at speech recognition level in recent years [24], although not quite yet at the human and even super-human performance levels reported in some public claims.

B. Language understanding

The natural language understanding (NLU) layer also presented good performance both for in-scope intent recognition and out-of-scope fallback triggering. The main pre-defined intents got $F(\beta = 0.5)$ around 0.98/0.99, showing therefore a very reliable performance. In general terms, yes/no and multiple choice questions worked smoothly and the issues at voice recognition level were frequently mitigated by the NLU layer, getting the right semantic interpretation of the children’s input.

However, the detailed analysis of recognition errors and OOS showed potential issues in around 10% of the inputs. We expected these issues to be reduced over time, as children learned how to interact with the system, but we did not observe this reduction. Maybe a longer experiment beyond 2 weeks would have shown an improvement, but our intuition, based on individual analysis of the audios transcripts, is that this 10% might be close to a hard limit with the current configuration and setup.

C. Dialogue management

At the dialogue level, mixed-initiative capabilities proved very useful. Children let the system drive the conversation in the first days while they discovered the activities available and how they work. Then, as they learned that they could take control and request their preferred activities, they started directing the conversation towards their interests. Notice that this is not an argument in favor of only user-driven dialogue: system-driven interactions were necessary for the children at the beginning to discover the system capabilities, and would be fundamental again in a context of dynamic content updates (e.g., new activities being added through the experiment).

The usage of *Help* and *Repeat* built-in intents was lower than we expected. Most children did not use these capabilities even once, probably they did not even think they could do it. For future experiments and similar applications, we believe that a more detailed explanation of the dialogue capabilities which can facilitate better interaction should be presented before interactions take place.

D. Limitations and future work

The findings of this study must be limited to and understood under the context in which the experiment was carried out. H4K’s activities were limited to the 5 described in section II-A and the interactions under study were divided in three basic categories: yes/no vs multiple choice vs open-ended questions. The experiments were also limited in terms of language (Spanish) and geographical location (Spain).

To overcome these limitations and expand the research scope, a follow-up experiment using H4K is already under

preparation. This new experiment will be more ambitious in multiple dimensions:

- **More diverse:** including more languages and better geographic and demographic diversity among the participants
- **Wider scope:** Longer cohabitation time and more participants
- **More functionalities:** More activities available, more elaborate multi-turn subdialogues and activity recommendations based on user profiling.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The main contributions of this CRI language study in children's home are:

- We show that, even in this challenging scenario, the speech recognition and language understanding layers can perform reliably. This aligns with Xu and Warschauer [10], who reported a rate of inaccurate intent classifications of only 0.3%-0.7% for interactions with CAs. Based on our study, we recommend increasing the research focus on the dialogue management level.
- We share how providing mixed-initiative dialogue capabilities is very beneficial for the user experience as they learn how to use the system, with a shifting from mostly system-driven interactions in the first days to mostly user-driven by the end of the experiment.
- We analyse some common dialogue patterns and conclude that "help" and "repeat" functionalities requires explicit training of the user. On the other hand, a safety-net "background" strategy should be included always in this kind of conversational applications.

In addition to these insights, we share a number of statistics about turn taking, dialogue closure and error analysis that could be helpful for future systems design.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Potamianos, S. Narayanan, and S. Lee, "Automatic speech recognition for children," in *Fifth European Conference on Speech Communication and Technology*, 1997.
- [2] M. Russell and S. D'Arcy, "Challenges for computer recognition of children's speech," in *Workshop on speech and language technology in education*, 2007.
- [3] H. Liao, G. Pundak, O. Siohan, M. Carroll, N. Coccaro, Q.-M. Jiang, T. N. Sainath, A. Senior, F. Beaufays, and M. Bacchiani, "Large vocabulary automatic speech recognition for children," 2015.
- [4] S. S. Gray, D. Willett, J. Lu, J. Pinto, P. Maergner, and N. Bodenstab, "Child automatic speech recognition for us english: child interaction with living-room-electronic-devices." in *WOCCI*, 2014, pp. 21–26.
- [5] C. L. van Straten, J. Peter, and R. Kühne, "Child-robot relationship formation: A narrative review of empirical research," *International Journal of Social Robotics*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 325–344, 2020.
- [6] Z. Zhao and R. McEwen, "'let's read a book together' a long-term study on the usage of pre-school children with their home companion robot," in *Proceedings of the 2022 ACM/IEEE International Conference on Human-Robot Interaction*, 2022, pp. 24–32.
- [7] J. E. Michaelis and B. Mutlu, "Reading socially: Transforming the in-home reading experience with a learning-companion robot," *Science Robotics*, vol. 3, no. 21, p. eaat5999, 2018.
- [8] R. Garg, H. Cui, S. Seligson, B. Zhang, M. Porcheron, L. Clark, B. R. Cowan, and E. Beneteau, "The last decade of hci research on children and voice-based conversational agents," in *Proceedings of the 2022 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, 2022, pp. 1–19.
- [9] E. Beneteau, O. K. Richards, M. Zhang, J. A. Kientz, J. Yip, and A. Hiniker, "Communication breakdowns between families and alexa," in *Proceedings of the 2019 CHI conference on human factors in computing systems*, 2019, pp. 1–13.
- [10] Y. Xu and M. Warschauer, "Exploring young children's engagement in joint reading with a conversational agent," in *Proceedings of the interaction design and children conference*, 2020, pp. 216–228.
- [11] —, "'elinor is talking to me on the screen!' integrating conversational agents into children's television programming," in *Extended Abstracts of the 2020 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, 2020, pp. 1–8.
- [12] I. Monarca, F. L. Cibrian, A. Mendoza, G. Hayes, and M. Tentori, "Why doesn't the conversational agent understand me? a language analysis of children speech," in *Adjunct proceedings of the 2020 ACM international joint conference on pervasive and ubiquitous computing and proceedings of the 2020 ACM international symposium on wearable computers*, 2020, pp. 90–93.
- [13] L. Levinson, G. A. Garcia, G. Perez, G. Alvarez-Benito, J. G. Amores, M. Castaño-Ocaña, M. Castro-Malet, R. Gomez, and S. Šabanović, "Living with haru4kids: Child and parent perceptions of a co-habitation robot for children," in *Social Robotics: 14th International Conference, ICSR 2022, Florence, Italy, December 13–16, 2022, Proceedings, Part II*. Springer, 2023, pp. 54–63.
- [14] R. Gomez, D. Szapiro, K. Galindo, and K. Nakamura, "'haru': Hardware design of an experimental tabletop robot assistant," in *2018 13th ACM/IEEE International Conference on Human-Robot Interaction (HRI)*. IEEE, 2018, pp. 233–240.
- [15] E. Nichols, S. R. Siskind, L. Ivanchuk, G. Pérez, W. Kamino, S. Šabanović, and R. Gomez, "Hey haru, let's be friends!" in *Proceedings of IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)*. IEEE, 2022.
- [16] Google.Com, "Dialogflow," Oct. 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://cloud.google.com/dialogflow/>
- [17] V. Charisi, E. Gomez, G. Mier, L. Merino, and R. Gomez, "Child-robot collaborative problem-solving and the importance of child's voluntary interaction: a developmental perspective," *Frontiers in Robotics and AI*, vol. 7, p. 15, 2020.
- [18] D. Leyzberg, A. Ramachandran, and B. Scassellati, "The effect of personalization in longer-term robot tutoring," *ACM Transactions on Human-Robot Interaction (THRI)*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 1–19, 2018.
- [19] J. M. Kory-Westlund and C. Breazeal, "A long-term study of young children's rapport, social emulation, and language learning with a peer-like robot playmate in preschool," *Frontiers in Robotics and AI*, vol. 6, p. 81, 2019.
- [20] Amazon.Com, "Cloudwatch," Oct. 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://aws.amazon.com/cloudwatch>
- [21] S. Larson, A. Mahendran, J. J. Peper, C. Clarke, A. Lee, P. Hill, J. K. Kummerfeld, K. Leach, M. A. Laurenzano, L. Tang et al., "An evaluation dataset for intent classification and out-of-scope prediction," *arXiv preprint arXiv:1909.02027*, 2019.
- [22] M. A. Walker, D. J. Litman, C. A. Kamm, and A. Abella, "Paradise: A framework for evaluating spoken dialogue agents," *arXiv preprint cmp-lg/9704004*, 1997.
- [23] P. Ljunglöf, S. Larsson, K. H. Mühlenbock, and G. Thunberg, "Trik: A talking and drawing robot for children with communication disabilities," in *Proceedings of the 17th Nordic Conference of Computational Linguistics (NODALIDA 2009)*, 2009, pp. 275–278.
- [24] J. Li, "Recent advances in end-to-end automatic speech recognition," *APSIPA Transactions on Signal and Information Processing*, vol. 11, no. 1, 2022.